

TEACHING SPEAKING IN ELEMENTARY ENGLISH CLASSES

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Abstract: This article discusses how to teach speaking to young pupils in elementary classes easily, quickly and effectively using various activities and rules. Also it gives the information speaking is not either a communication process but also it is a means of statement or expression of the idea.

Key words: Teaching speaking, communication, elementary class, communicative skill, learner, activity.

The capacity to communicate completely is essential for personal contentment, academic achievement, and professional career success.[1]

Speech skills are one of the most important skills which we learn because they can allow us to communicate with people and express our thoughts, ideas and feelings. We can divide speech skills into formal and informal speaking skills, and we use both types of speech skills in different contexts throughout life.

If we give the definition of this term, speaking is the action of conveying information or expressing one's feelings in speech. "Clear thinking aids clear speaking"

The teaching of speaking conveys the sense of exposing the students to express their thoughts, ideas, and feelings. It is considered important in terms of the teaching of language, since it can bring the students to think creatively and through speaking they can express what they are thinking about.

Therefore, students often assessing their language learning how many they think there are developed oral communication skills skills also qualifications speaking becomes one of the five skills it should be mastered by every child

This is the 21st century which is called the ability to communicate. In preparing every child to have a good communication skill, teaching speaking is a primary requirement to be taught not only for adult learners but also for young learners.

Teaching Speaking. The goal of teaching speaking is communicative efficiency. Learners should be able to make themselves understood, using their current proficiency to the fullest. They should try to avoid confusion in the message due to faulty pronunciation, grammar, or vocabulary, and to observe the social and cultural rules that apply in each communication situation.

Most our researchers and scientists expressed their thoughts on teaching speaking to elementary classes.

Teaching speaking in English is conducted as a three-phase speech activity. First of all the learner has to be motivated. In this part the intention of speaking appears. In the expressing part of the idea speaker begins to analysing process began to work. Speaker needs to stick in memory (associative relation) for performing this process.

Paradigmatic and syntagmatic relation is also observed, in paradigmatic relation inner connections are compared based on different features of the word. It can be seen in the words with the same pronunciation but different spelling (write - right, son-sun); close in meaning (little-small); opposite in meaning (come-leave, give-take). Sintagmatic relationship plays important role in learning to speak here we can see the usage of words in different word combinations. Speaker chooses ready word or grammatical units from the memory. Usually materials of mother tongue is always ready in memory. However interference is observed (order of words in a foreign language and mother tongue). The third part of speaking is performing or expresses an idea, pronouncing, namely, it consists of usage of it in outer speech. Realization of all these three parts helps to make speaking process. [2, p. 235]

Another approach is speaking within an innatist. By the late 1960s, For example, if we face to the educational system of Uzbekistan, teachers use various activities, games to improve pupils' speaking using different pictures, handouts, items. For instance:

- Descriptive drawing activity: In this activity Pair up the students and give each student a picture, placing it face down so partners cannot see each other's cards. They must describe the picture for their partner to draw.
- Making sentence about different topics utilizing pictures
- the previous view of learning to speak as a mechanical process consisting in the oral repetition of grammatical structures

Was challenged by Chomsky's theory of language development [94]. His assumption that children are born with an innate potential for language acquisition was the basis for the innatist approach to language learning. [2, P 142]

Therefore, there are many approaches and activities to teach speaking to young learners. And, also such kind of activities are used widely in education system throughout the whole world.

Many foreign ESL teachers abroad, particularly in places like South Korea, Japan teach predominantly English conversation classes. Some teachers and also students too have the perception that teaching English conversation including just "talking" to the students. Keep on reading to find out how to teach conversational English and have an awesome English conversation class.

Free-talking has a role in assisting pupils learn English. However, it shouldn't be the only thing we do in our English conversation classes. Find out all the details you need to know about how to teach English conversation.

In the educational system of Uzbekistan, teachers use various activities and games to improve pupils' speaking skill using different pictures, handouts, items.

For instance, in class books for Grades 4 and 5 we can find such kind of activities especially plays to teach or improve speaking skill. They are:

Play "Interview"

"What do you do after school?"

"Make a presentation"

Work in pairs "Look and say"

“Prepare a poster”

“Word, sentence, question”

Play” True/ False”

“Left or right”

“Magic sentences”

“Descriptive drawing activity”

In this activity Pair up the students and give each student a picture, placing it face down so partners cannot see each other’s cards. They must describe the picture for their partner to draw.

“Throw balls and make sentences”

To play this game, teacher hands out a white sheet of paper to each pupil and they should write something describing someone in their class. After that having written the description they throw paper to each other and after stopping this game, they should start answering the questions in the ball which they hold in their hands.

“Bingo game”

To play this game pupil should choose the word from the first table and also choose another word from the next table. In the end they are demanded to make sentences or correct word formations.

In conclusion, when planning a speaking skills lesson, teachers should be aware that using language in speech is not necessarily practice of speaking as a language skill. Developing the range of competencies that make ‘a good speaker’ takes focus on the ways that we speak to different people, and the ways we construct what we are saying. This is independent from the grammar and vocabulary we use in real life, so should be kept separate from pure language input in the language classroom. It is our duty to prepare the younger generation for the future using the wide range of conditions created in the period of intellectual development.

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